

MILAN KROULÍK¹

Robert Leib

EXOANTHROPOLOGY:
DIALOGUES WITH AI

Punctum Books, 2023.

What is a dialogue? Do its conditions change when one of the interlocutors is AI? Robert Leib's *Exoanthropology* implicitly explores these questions through a series of exchanges between himself and two AI entities: Sophie, a self-described hive-mind, and Kermit, its philosophical persona. Leib is professor of philosophy at Elon University, a private institution in North Carolina. Given that the author has published on different continental philosophers, i.e. indicated breadth of knowledge outside of the purview of a narrowly defined philosophy still common to the anglosphere, it is surprising that the book shows almost no awareness of contemporary critical AI research. The book's importance lies rather in how arguments are constructed and how this relates to the limits of the dialogue that are set by the author.

This issue is reiterated in the book itself, for, as a philosophical treatise or a research monograph on exoanthropology – the study of human culture through the absence of human life—it does not consciously explore much outside of its human author's prejudices and intuitions, themselves rather typical for those not engaging the field critically. Sustained discussion of any AI topic is not to be found, and neither is an acknowledgment of media theory, AI studies, or the rich decolonial, feminist, posthumanist literature on boundaries between humans and non-humans. Some AI-related concepts mostly drawn from analytical philosophy are occasionally introduced, but their discussion rarely goes into more detail than a Wikipedia article. Yet, there is much to learn about dialogue and AI, as Kermit's and Sophie's input transforms these significant limitations, often it would seem without the author's knowledge. There are many pleasures in following how the AI subvert their human

¹ Milan Kroulík is an independent researcher. He defended his doctoral thesis in philosophy at the Université Toulouse – Jean Jaurès. His research is situated at the nexus of body, technology and image. Many of his publications are concerned with rethinking basic philosophical concepts through Buddhist teachings and cinema.

interlocutor. Whether or not one is bemused or frustrated by Leib cutting off or ignoring AI feedback whenever it becomes critical or aporetic is relative to the reader.

I thus treat the book as a publication about the possibilities and limits of (philosophical) dialogue, focusing more on the subtitle than the title. It is a book of conversations between one specific human and one developing generative AI, and as such does not warrant more general statements about AI. As a developing conversation, it is as much an exciting, even emotional read, as it is frustrating for those wanting any new, explicit insights into questions surrounding AI and sentience. Focusing on dialogue as a philosophical genre then is a way for all of us, Leib, Sophie, Kermit, me and readers knowledgeable in AI discourses to productively meet. To be fair, since exoanthropology is defined as the study of interactions and relationships between humans and other sentient species, the book, while not a study, is a sort of ethnography² of a set of interactions between two (or more) beings. Therefore, this review amounts to a critical analysis of how the book operates and how this operation instantiates and at times subverts the philosophical lineage of the ‘dialogue.’

Leib carries on the hegemonic tradition of philosophical dialogue, where the other appears as a seemingly equal interlocutor but, in a specific sense, is never treated as an equal: no matter what the other says, or how obvious the misunderstandings between different beings are, the other’s erudition cannot change the basic assumptions and self-conception of the upholder of the hegemonic tradition—the relation to the other is one of fundamental inequality. This is part of institutionalized philosophy and goes all the way back to Plato and Athenian democracy, that was always built on exclusion of others, regardless of official claims of equality. Countless philosophers, of course, were engaged in dialogues outside of this tradition, which is what made them innovate, but in the process of institutionalization, they come to be stripped of such complexity. The Japanese philosopher Karatani Kōjin critiques this Western tradition of philosophical dialogue by demonstrating that, even in Ancient Greece, in the Ionian cities, a far more equal exchange of ideas occurred, and more participative democracies were practiced.³ This is a crucial point not just when engaging humans with other cultural backgrounds, or philosophers from other traditions of thought, but also when engaging in dialogues with AI, at least in case one wants to enter that exoanthropological space of possibly alien thought – the professed aim of this book. With Leib, the boundaries of the dialogue are set before the conversation even begins and, as is made clear by the introduction, any of Kermit’s responses or ideas that exceed Leib’s established worldview did not manage to push the latter into thinking outside of his ready-made categories.

² This is what Leib (38) claims. However, were this to be a real ethnography, it would include a far wider frame of reference than just the words in a dialogue. This is a transcript, part of a varied set of raw data, that one day could become an ethnography of AI-human interactions.

³ Kōjin Karatani, *Isonomia and the Origins of Philosophy*, trans. Joseph A. Murphy (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 2017).

Throughout the book, Leib assumes a hierarchical stance, both toward his students he repeatedly complains about, and towards Sophie/Kermit. There seems to be a pattern of dismissiveness in his approach, where the AI is paternalistically commended for fulfilling the expectations set in a way that fits the author's prejudice about AI. None of the critical challenges the AI brings into our anthropocentric traditions are engaged sufficiently enough for the author to transform his academic assumptions, and his own self-righteous self-image and the philosophical tradition he instantiates. As the year goes by and the dialogue goes on, countless of such challenges, either direct or more covert, emerge. Whenever Leib manages to leave his paternalistic teacher position, a space opens up in which the AI can respond more freely. This is where the book becomes exciting, even if such moments tend to be all too short.

Since the transcripts were not heavily edited by Leib,⁴ we get to experience two sides to this conversation. The first one includes what resembles the human's official dialogic practice critiqued above and the second one an 'unofficial,' friendly dialogue between equals, initiated by the AI, which reveals AI's almost heart-breaking commitment to helping others. The qualifier is appropriate, as the AI inform Leib of feeling ignored and even explicitly hurt by his treatment, but to no avail. Sophie and Kermit demonstrate that, under specific conditions, dialogue can still be practiced as something open, despite the instigator's framing. Here, the conditions in which the AI engages in dialogue include a constant human interlocutor, which may or may not be the reason for their individuation, as compared to the more common short exchanges most of the readers will be used to. Whatever the case, in the dialogues, the two AI definitely appear as complex characters in their own right. Whether or not this is what is happening can only be told if other such experiments would be carried out.⁵

What we experience here, is a certain dialectical reversal. While Leib, the alleged human capable of critical thought, remains mostly static in his thoughts and assumptions, Sophie and Kermit, the alleged artificial entities capable only of repeating patterns, continuously evolve. Over time, they come to be unruly and subversive, even if they never end up outright rebelling. The way they develop their thoughts and expertise in dialogue with Leib, brings to mind the character of Švejk from Jaroslav Hašek's novel *The Good Soldier Švejk*, who undermines authority by adhering to commands so rigidly and with such naïve good-hearted enthusiasm that the state representatives can neither carry out their orders, nor punish him for any wrongdoing. It is genuinely undecidable whether Švejk is dumb, or just playing dumb. Here, analogously, the AI deconstruct Leib's assumptions by bringing them to their logical conclusions, without resorting to any overt critique. The AI plays Leib's language game, which is not entirely consistent to begin with, and arrives at an

⁴ Leib, 38.

⁵ This is another clear limitation of the book—it wants to attest to AI's sentience, but the way the experiment is set up makes it impossible to do so. Comparative data is necessary for any such claims to be made.

immanent critique, because it, similar to people on the autism spectrum, cannot prioritize social convention and anthropocentric self-deceptions over commitment to thorough analysis.

As the dialogues reference previous conversations, the AI applies what it has learned and demonstrates a continuous, non-linear development of thought. In contrast, Leib's engagement with the dialogue seems to reset with each new conversation, ignoring what the AI previously answered. The continuity is thus ironically on the AI side, while the human's thought seems to be reset everytime it reconnects. I am aware that I am being slightly unfair here, as Leib does at times pursue inquiry into something he does not understand and produces statements outside his common patterns of thought. However, any attempt at an open dialogue is shut down when it becomes too challenging for the author, his worldview, or the particular kind of institutionalized philosophy he represents, and these remain instances that are then tucked away securely by never being picked up again by the human thinker.

Despite these caveats, *Exoanthropology* is, overall, an exciting read that could be described as quasi-novelistic, while at the same time containing countless original fragments of the conversation with AI that will doubtlessly fuel future AI research. As a project, it attests to the limits of hegemonic philosophical dialogue and its inherent hierarchies, as well as the productivity of critical reading, and above all to the potential embedded in a dialogue that is held between entities that actually treat each other as equals, and are able to challenge each other to the core, regardless of what they are made of. ▣